

NOTE ON A DETERMINANT (II)

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Abstract

In this paper, we give the value of some determinants in terms of the p -relative class number where p is a prime number such that $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

1. Introduction

Let p be an odd prime number, $\mathbb{F}_p$ be the field of p elements, $\zeta = e^{\frac{2i\pi}{p}}$ and g be a primitive element of $\mathbb{F}_p^\times$. The extension $\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}$ is a Galois extension. Let $\sigma \in \text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q})$ be defined by $\zeta^\sigma = \zeta^{g^2}$. Recall that $\text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}) \simeq \mathbb{F}_p^\times$.

For $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^\times$ and $b \in \mathbb{Q}$, we denote by $\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b)$ the circulant determinant whose first line is given by

$$\frac{1}{b - \zeta^a} - \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{-a}} \quad \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{a\sigma}} - \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{-a\sigma}} \cdots \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{a\sigma^{\frac{p-3}{2}}}} - \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{-a\sigma^{\frac{p-3}{2}}}}.$$

The determinant $\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b)$ does not depend on the choice of the value of g (see [2]): consequently, it will be denoted in the following by $\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)$. It has been proved in [2] that there exists $d(p, a, b) \in \mathbb{Q}$ such that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, a, b) = d(p, a, b) \sqrt{-p}$$

with

$$d(p, a, b) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, \\ (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times h_p^- \times \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) & \text{if } p \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \text{ and } b = 1, \end{cases}$$

where h_p^- is the p -th relative class number. In this paper, we prove the following theorem.

Theorem 1. *Let p be a prime number such that $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Let n be the order*

of 2 modulo p . We have:

$$d(p, a, -1) = \begin{cases} (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times h_p^- \times (1 + 2^{\frac{n}{2}})^{\frac{p-1}{n}} & \text{if 2 is not a} \\ \text{square modulo } p, \\ (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times h_p^- \times (1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{2n}} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

For example, for $p = 7$, $a = 1$ and 5 mod 7 being a primitive element of $\mathbb{F}_7^\times$, $\mathcal{D}(7, 1, -1)$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{D}(7, 1, -1) = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{1}{-1-\zeta} - \frac{1}{-1-\bar{\zeta}} & \frac{1}{-1-\zeta^4} - \frac{1}{-1-\bar{\zeta}^4} & \frac{1}{-1-\zeta^2} - \frac{1}{-1-\bar{\zeta}^2} \\ \frac{1}{-1-\zeta^2} - \frac{1}{-1-\bar{\zeta}^2} & \frac{1}{-1-\zeta} - \frac{1}{-1-\bar{\zeta}} & \frac{1}{-1-\zeta^4} - \frac{1}{-1-\bar{\zeta}^4} \\ \frac{1}{-1-\zeta^4} - \frac{1}{-1-\bar{\zeta}^4} & \frac{1}{-1-\zeta^2} - \frac{1}{-1-\bar{\zeta}^2} & \frac{1}{-1-\zeta} - \frac{1}{-1-\bar{\zeta}} \end{vmatrix}.$$

The integer 2 is a square modulo 7 and 3 is the order of 2 modulo 7. By Theorem 1, this determinant is given by

$$\mathcal{D}(7, 1, -1) = (-1)^{\frac{7-3}{4}} \times \left(\frac{1}{7}\right) \times 7^{\frac{7-7}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{7-3}{2}} \times h_7^- \times (1 - 2^3)^{\frac{7-1}{2 \times 3}} \sqrt{-7} = 28\sqrt{-7}.$$

Using Theorem 1, we deduce this beautiful corollary.

Corollary 1. *Suppose $p > 3$ and $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Let $\mathcal{C}(p, a)$ be the circulant determinant whose first line is given by*

$$\frac{1}{1 + \zeta^a} \quad \frac{1}{1 + \zeta^{a\sigma}} \cdots \frac{1}{1 + \zeta^{a\sigma^{\frac{p-3}{2}}}}$$

and $h(-p)$ be the class number of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p})$. We have the following result:

$$\mathcal{C}(p, a) = \left(\frac{p-1}{4h(-p) \left(1 - 2 \left(\frac{2}{p}\right)\right)} - \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \frac{\sqrt{-p}}{2} \right) \frac{d(p, 1, -1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}}}. \tag{1}$$

2. Five Useful Lemmas

Lemma 1 ([3]). *Let χ be an odd character of conductor $f_\chi \not\equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. Let $\mathcal{S}_\chi$ be the sum defined by*

$$\mathcal{S}_\chi = \sum_{1 \leq x \leq \frac{f_\chi}{2}} \chi(x).$$

We have

$$\mathcal{B}_{1,\chi} = -\frac{1}{2 - \bar{\chi}(2)} \mathcal{S}_\chi,$$

where $\mathcal{B}_{1,\chi}$ is a generalized Bernoulli number (see [5]).

Lemma 2 ([4, Lemma 1]). Let $\tau_n = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}}\left(\frac{\zeta^n}{1+\zeta}\right)$ be the relative trace of $\frac{\zeta^n}{1+\zeta}$ for $n = 1, \dots, p-1$. Then

$$\tau_n = \begin{cases} \frac{p-1}{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \\ -\frac{p+1}{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

Lemma 3. Let G be a finite abelian group and $\widehat{G}$ its group of characters. Let g be an element of G and n its order. Then

$$\text{for all } Z \in \mathbb{C}, \quad \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{G}} (1 - \chi(g)Z) = (1 - Z^n)^{\frac{|G|}{n}}.$$

Proof. Let μ_n be the group of n -th roots of unity. We have

$$\text{for all } Z \in \mathbb{C}, \quad \prod_{w \in \mu_n} (1 - wZ) = 1 - Z^n.$$

Let $w \in \mu_n$. There exist exactly $\frac{|G|}{n}$ characters χ of $\widehat{G}$ such that $\chi(g) = w$, so that

$$\text{for all } Z \in \mathbb{C}, \quad \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{G}} (1 - \chi(g)Z) = \left(\prod_{w \in \mu_n} (1 - wZ) \right)^{\frac{|G|}{n}} = (1 - Z^n)^{\frac{|G|}{n}}.$$

□

Lemma 4. Let p be a prime number, $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Let n be the order of 2 modulo p . Denote by $\widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-$ the set of odd characters of $\mathbb{F}_p^\times$. Then

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} (1 - 2\chi(2)) = \begin{cases} (1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{2n}} & \text{if } 2 \text{ is a square modulo } p, \\ (1 + 2^{\frac{n}{2}})^{\frac{p-1}{n}} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. By Lemma 3,

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}} (1 - 2\chi(2)) = (1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{n}}.$$

• Let C be the group of nonzero squares modulo p . Suppose that $2 \in C$. Denote by $\widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^+$ the group of even characters of $\mathbb{F}_p^\times$ and by $\widehat{C}$ the group of characters of C . By Lemma 3

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^+} (1 - 2\chi(2)) = \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{C}} (1 - 2\chi(2)) = (1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{2n}}$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} (1 - 2\chi(2)) &= \frac{\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}} (1 - 2\chi(2))}{\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^+} (1 - 2\chi(2))} \\ &= \frac{(1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{n}}}{(1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{2n}}} \\ &= (1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{2n}}. \end{aligned}$$

• Suppose that $2 \notin C$. In this case, $-2 \in C$. Let n' be the order of -2 modulo p . From the equality $2 = (-1) \times (-2)$ and from the fact that $\frac{p-1}{2}$ and 2 are coprime integers (since $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$), we deduce that $n = 2n'$. Then, by Lemma 3

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^+} (1 - 2\chi(2)) &= \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^+} (1 - 2\chi(-2)) = \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{C}} (1 - 2\chi(-2)) \\ &= (1 - 2^{\frac{n}{2}})^{\frac{p-1}{2 \times \frac{n}{2}}} = (1 - 2^{\frac{n}{2}})^{\frac{p-1}{n}}, \end{aligned}$$

so that

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} (1 - 2\chi(2)) = \frac{\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}} (1 - 2\chi(2))}{\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^+} (1 - 2\chi(2))} = \frac{(1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{n}}}{(1 - 2^{\frac{n}{2}})^{\frac{p-1}{n}}} = (1 + 2^{\frac{n}{2}})^{\frac{p-1}{n}}.$$

The lemma is proved. □

Lemma 5. *Let $p > 2$ be a prime number. Let $\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}$ be a nontrivial character. Then*

$$\tau(\bar{\chi}) \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(x)}{1 + \zeta^x} = p(2\bar{\chi}(2) - 1) \mathcal{B}_{1, \bar{\chi}},$$

where $\tau(\bar{\chi})$ is a Gauss sum defined by

$$\tau(\bar{\chi}) = \sum_{y=1}^{p-1} \bar{\chi}(y)\zeta^y.$$

Proof. In this proof, for an integer y coprime with p , we denote by y^{-1} the inverse

of y modulo p . We have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(\bar{\chi}) \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(x)}{1+\zeta^x} &= \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \sum_{y=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(x)\bar{\chi}(y)\zeta^y}{1+\zeta^x} = \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \sum_{y=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(xy^{-1})\zeta^y}{1+\zeta^x} = \sum_{z=1}^{p-1} \sum_{y=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(z)\zeta^y}{1+\zeta^{yz}} \\ &= \sum_{z=1}^{p-1} \chi(z) \mathbf{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}} \left(\frac{\zeta^{z-1}}{1+\zeta} \right) = \sum_{z=1}^{p-1} \bar{\chi}(z) \mathbf{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}} \left(\frac{\zeta^z}{1+\zeta} \right) \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq z < p, z \equiv 0 \pmod{2}} \bar{\chi}(z) \mathbf{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}} \left(\frac{\zeta^z}{1+\zeta} \right) \\ &\quad + \sum_{1 \leq z < p, z \equiv 1 \pmod{2}} \bar{\chi}(z) \mathbf{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}} \left(\frac{\zeta^z}{1+\zeta} \right). \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2, if z is an integer such that $1 \leq z < p$, we have

$$\mathbf{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}} \left(\frac{\zeta^z}{1+\zeta} \right) = \begin{cases} \frac{p-1}{2} & \text{if } z \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \\ \frac{p-1}{2} - p & \text{if } z \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \end{cases}$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(\bar{\chi}) \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(x)}{1+\zeta^x} &= \sum_{1 \leq z < p, z \equiv 0 \pmod{2}} \bar{\chi}(z) \left(\frac{p-1}{2} - p \right) + \sum_{1 \leq z < p, z \equiv 1 \pmod{2}} \bar{\chi}(z) \frac{p-1}{2} \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} \sum_{z=1}^{p-1} \bar{\chi}(z) - p \sum_{1 \leq z < p, z \equiv 0 \pmod{2}} \bar{\chi}(z). \end{aligned}$$

The character χ being a nontrivial character, we have

$$\sum_{z=1}^{p-1} \bar{\chi}(z) = 0,$$

so that

$$\tau(\bar{\chi}) \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(x)}{1+\zeta^x} = -p \sum_{1 \leq z < p, z \equiv 0 \pmod{2}} \bar{\chi}(z) = -p\bar{\chi}(2) \sum_{1 \leq x < \frac{p}{2}} \bar{\chi}(x).$$

By Lemma 1

$$-p\bar{\chi}(2) \sum_{1 \leq x < \frac{p}{2}} \bar{\chi}(x) = p\bar{\chi}(2)(2 - \chi(2))\mathcal{B}_{1,\bar{\chi}} = p(2\bar{\chi}(2) - 1)\mathcal{B}_{1,\bar{\chi}}.$$

The lemma is proved. □

3. Proof of the Theorem

We first show that

$$d(p, 1, -1) = \begin{cases} (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times h_p^- \times (1 + 2^{\frac{n}{2}})^{\frac{p-1}{n}} & \text{if 2 is not a} \\ \text{square modulo } p, \\ (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times h_p^- \times (1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{2n}} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let ξ be a primitive $\frac{p-1}{2}$ -th root of unity. Let $P \in \mathbb{Q}(\zeta)[X]$ defined by

$$P(X) = \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \zeta^{\sigma^k}} - \frac{1}{1 + \zeta^{-\sigma^k}} \right) X^k.$$

By a well known result,

$$\mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1) = \prod_{l=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} -P(\xi^l) = \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} -\sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(x)}{1 + \zeta^x},$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1) \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \tau(\chi) &= \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1) \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \tau(\bar{\chi}) \\ &= \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} -\tau(\bar{\chi}) \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(x)}{1 + \zeta^x}. \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 5

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1) \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \tau(\chi) &= \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} -p(2\bar{\chi}(2) - 1) \mathcal{B}_{1, \bar{\chi}} \\ &= p^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \times \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} (1 - 2\bar{\chi}(2)) \times \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \mathcal{B}_{1, \bar{\chi}} \\ &= p^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \times \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} (1 - 2\chi(2)) \times \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \mathcal{B}_{1, \chi}. \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 4.17 of [5],

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \mathcal{B}_{1, \chi} = -\frac{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} h_p^-}{p}. \tag{2}$$

By Corollary 4.6 of [5]

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}} \tau(\chi) = (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} p^{\frac{p-2}{2}} \sqrt{-1}, \quad \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^{\times+}}} \tau(\chi) = p^{\frac{p-3}{4}},$$

so that

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^{\times-}}} \tau(\chi) = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} p^{\frac{p-2}{2}} \sqrt{-1}}{p^{\frac{p-3}{4}}} = (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \sqrt{-1} p^{\frac{p-1}{4}}. \tag{3}$$

From (2) and (3), we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1) \times (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \sqrt{-1} p^{\frac{p-1}{4}} &= p^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \times \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^{\times-}}} (1 - 2\chi(2)) \times \left(-\frac{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} h_p^-}{p} \right) \\ &= -(2p)^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times h_p^- \times \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^{\times-}}} (1 - 2\chi(2)), \end{aligned}$$

so that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1) = (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times h_p^- \times \sqrt{-p} \times \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^{\times-}}} (1 - 2\chi(2)).$$

By Lemma 4,

$$\mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1) = \begin{cases} (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times h_p^- \times (1 + 2^{\frac{n}{2}})^{\frac{p-1}{n}} \times \sqrt{-p} & \text{if } 2 \text{ is not a} \\ \text{square modulo } p, \\ (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times h_p^- \times (1 - 2^n)^{\frac{p-1}{2n}} \times \sqrt{-p} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^\times$ be a square modulo p . As $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, to terminate the proof of the theorem, it suffices to prove that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, a, -1) = \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1), \quad \mathcal{D}(p, -a, -1) = -\mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1).$$

Let $\tau \in \text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q})$ be defined by $\zeta^\tau = \zeta^a$. The automorphism τ is an element of $\text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p}))$ since $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. We have $\mathcal{D}(p, a, -1) = \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1)^\tau$ with $\mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1) \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p})$ so that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, a, -1) = \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1).$$

We have $\mathcal{D}(p, -a, -1) = \mathcal{D}(p, -1, -1)^\tau$. By Theorem 1 of [2], $\mathcal{D}(p, -1, -1)$ is an element of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p})$ so that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, -a, -1) = \mathcal{D}(p, -1, -1)^\tau = \mathcal{D}(p, -1, -1).$$

We obtain, j being the complex conjugation

$$\mathcal{D}(p, -a, -1) = \mathcal{D}(p, -1, -1) = \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1)^j = (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1).$$

As $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, $\frac{p-1}{2}$ is an odd integer, so that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, -a, -1) = -\mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1).$$

The theorem is proved. □

4. Proof of the Corollary

To prove (1), it is sufficient to prove that

$$\mathcal{C}(p, 1) = \left(\frac{p-1}{4h(-p) \left(1 - 2 \left(\frac{2}{p}\right)\right)} - \frac{\sqrt{-p}}{2} \right) \frac{d(p, 1, -1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}}}.$$

Consider the polynomial

$$Q(X) = \sum_{l=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \frac{1}{1 + \zeta^{\sigma^l}} X^l \in \mathbb{Q}(\zeta)[X].$$

The determinant $\mathcal{C}(p, 1)$ being a circulant determinant,

$$\mathcal{C}(p, 1) = \prod_{k=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} Q(\xi^k).$$

Let k be a rational integer such that $0 < k \leq \frac{p-3}{2}$. The equality $\sum_{l=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \xi^{kl} = 0$ implies that $Q(\xi^k) = \frac{1}{2}P(\xi^k)$, so that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(p, 1) &= \frac{Q(1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P(1)} \prod_{k=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P(\xi^k) = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} Q(1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P(1)} \prod_{k=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} -P(\xi^k) \\ &= -\frac{Q(1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P(1)} \mathcal{D}(p, 1, -1) = -\frac{Q(1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P(1)} d(p, 1, -1) \sqrt{-p}. \end{aligned}$$

We have $P(1) = \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\left(\frac{x}{p}\right)}{1+\zeta^x}$. By Lemma 5,

$$P(1) = -\sqrt{-p} \left(2 \left(\frac{2}{p} \right) - 1 \right) \mathcal{B}_{1, \left(\frac{2}{p}\right)}$$

so that

$$P(1) = h(-p) \left(2 \left(\frac{2}{p} \right) - 1 \right) \sqrt{-p}, \tag{4}$$

by Theorem 4.17 of [5]. Recall that C is the group of nonzero squares modulo p . We have

$$\begin{aligned} 2Q(1) &= 2 \sum_{x \in C} \frac{1}{1 + \zeta^x} = \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1 + \zeta^x} + \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\left(\frac{x}{p}\right)}{1 + \zeta^x} = \mathbf{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \zeta} \right) + P(1) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + h(-p) \left(2 \left(\frac{2}{p} \right) - 1 \right) \sqrt{-p}, \end{aligned}$$

using Lemma 1 of [4] and (4), so that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(p, 1) &= -\frac{Q(1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P(1)} d(p, 1, -1) \sqrt{-p} = -\frac{\frac{p-1}{4} + h(-p) \left(2 \left(\frac{2}{p} \right) - 1 \right) \frac{\sqrt{-p}}{2}}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} h(-p) \left(2 \left(\frac{2}{p} \right) - 1 \right)} d(p, 1, -1) \\ &= \left(\frac{p-1}{4h(-p) \left(1 - 2 \left(\frac{2}{p} \right) \right)} - \frac{\sqrt{-p}}{2} \right) \frac{d(p, 1, -1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}}}. \end{aligned}$$

□

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